

Climate Change and Dengue Fever: Urgent Need for New Solutions Amidst Rising Cases and Limited Vaccine Supply

Issue/problem

Climate change has exacerbated the spread of multiple tropical diseases through [various mechanisms](#) while research into treatment and prevention of these diseases [does not reflect their expected impact on life expectancy](#). Amongst those diseases, recently increased temperatures have expanded [the geographical scope of mosquitoes carrying dengue fever](#). The virus traditionally affected countries near the Equator, but new cases have been reported as far as Europe.

Description of the problem

According to the Pan-American Health Organization, the number of suspected dengue fever cases has spiked to record highs in South America. The symptoms of dengue fever can be mild to fatal, and include [fever, headache, and muscle and joint pain](#). Currently, [there is no treatment for dengue fever](#), while the vaccine, Dengvaxia, is [only effective if an individual has already been infected](#). Moreover, the vaccine only protects against a single — out of a possible four — strain of the pathogen. Beyond the impact on health, a 2019 outbreak of dengue [is estimated to have reduced Brazil's GDP by 0.05%](#).

Results

QDenga – a new generation vaccine – is effective against all four strains. However, its manufacturer can only supply 5 million doses, [all of which have been purchased by Brazil](#) – a country of more than 160 million people. Other alternative dengue vaccines are currently in development, however [their efficacy is still under review](#).

Lessons learned

The current situation with dengue fever is symptomatic of the larger [market failures related to tropical diseases exacerbated by climate change](#). While new vaccines are being developed for dengue fever, demand far outstrips the current supply. Additionally, other diseases do not receive the same pharmaceutical research resource allocation due to a perception that [pharmaceuticals cannot be sold at a profitable price in these markets](#). [Public-private partnerships](#) can attenuate [these market failures](#) by [aligning incentives](#), and therefore motivate the development of novel prophylactics and treatments for tropical diseases.